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EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN HEALTHCARE INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This study analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of a comprehensive evaluation of the effectiveness of personnel management systems in healthcare institutions. It substantiates the necessity of considering institutional characteristics, staff composition, service quality, and the level of resource utilization when assessing management effectiveness. The importance of timely and well-grounded managerial decision-making is highlighted, and it is determined that delays or insufficient evaluation of such decisions can negatively affect labor productivity and overall organizational performance.

Furthermore, the study identifies key criteria for evaluating managerial decisions, including the degree of goal achievement, economic efficiency, and employee job satisfaction. Based on the Donabedian model, the quality of healthcare services is systematically analyzed through three components: structure, process, and outcome. In addition, a comprehensive assessment of labor productivity, service volume, staff turnover, and socio-economic indicators is considered an essential factor in optimizing the management system.

As a result, it is concluded that improving management effectiveness in healthcare institutions requires a multifactorial and systematic approach, which plays a crucial role in ensuring service quality and system sustainability.

Keywords: healthcare system, personnel management, management effectiveness, Donabedian model, labor productivity, service quality, economic efficiency, human resource policy, resource utilization, socio-economic indicators, managerial decisions.

INTRODUCTION.

In the healthcare sector, the development of a comprehensive methodology for evaluating the effectiveness of personnel management systems requires taking into account the specific characteristics of the institution, staff composition, service quality, and the level of resource utilization. Only through the integration of these factors is it possible to select an effective management approach appropriate for solving existing problems. In practice, the failure to implement managerial decisions in a timely manner or making decisions without sufficient evaluation leads to a decline in employee performance, reduced labor productivity, and negatively affects the overall economic indicators of the organization.

Therefore, the development of a methodology for assessing the effectiveness of personnel management systems in healthcare institutions and its application within the framework of the institution's development strategy constitute an essential component of the concept of optimizing personnel management. The World Health Organization [1,3] also recognizes the evaluation of management effectiveness as a key condition for ensuring the sustainability of the healthcare system and improving service quality.

The evaluation of the effectiveness of managerial decisions performs several important functions in the activities of healthcare institutions. In particular, it contributes to improving the quality of personnel management, forecasting potential problems, determining the expected effectiveness of decisions at the initial stage, assessing intermediate results during implementation, and analyzing the ratio between costs and achieved outcomes at the final stage.

LITERATURE REVIEW.

Scientific studies indicate that the evaluation of managerial decisions should be based on the integration of three key components: first, the degree of achievement of defined objectives; second, economic efficiency, meaning the optimal ratio between costs and outcomes; and third, employee job satisfaction and social protection [5]. This approach plays a crucial role in ensuring managerial stability in healthcare institutions.

The effectiveness of management in the healthcare system largely depends on the proper formulation of human resource policies, the implementation of the principles of organizational democracy, and the existence of programs aimed at improving labor productivity. Researchers emphasize that investment in human resources is one of the most important factors in improving both service quality and economic outcomes in healthcare institutions [2,3].

A clear example of this is the Donabedian model, one of the most widely used conceptual frameworks for evaluating healthcare service quality. This model proposes assessing quality through three main components: structure, process, and outcome. Structure refers to the conditions necessary for healthcare delivery, such as facilities, equipment, personnel, and financial resources. Process includes interactions with patients and clinical practices such as diagnosis, treatment, and prevention. Outcome reflects changes in patients' health status, satisfaction levels, and other performance indicators [4,7]. Through this framework, healthcare institutions can evaluate service quality and effectiveness on a solid scientific basis, as structure influences processes, and processes directly determine outcomes [10].

The Donabedian model is used not only for assessing clinical outcomes but also for understanding cause-and-effect relationships in healthcare systems. It is based on research in healthcare management and quality monitoring, emphasizing the importance of both structure and process for effective service delivery. In other words, well-structured healthcare institutions tend to generate more efficient processes, which in turn lead to better outcomes [8,9]. This model supports a systematic, data-driven, and outcome-oriented approach to decision-making in healthcare quality management.

At the same time, labor productivity is considered a key economic indicator in evaluating the performance of healthcare institutions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

In international practice, productivity is often expressed through the concepts of "effect" and "efficiency." Effect refers to the achievement of the objectives set for an institution, while efficiency denotes the ratio of useful outcomes to the resources expended to achieve them. For example, a medical institution may achieve a positive effect by increasing the volume of services provided or expanding the range of healthcare services [13].

However, the assessment of healthcare institutions' performance cannot be considered complete without a comprehensive accounting of costs. Therefore, indicators of efficiency include profit, the volume of medical services provided, labor discipline, staff turnover, and employee job satisfaction. These socio-economic indicators play a crucial role in determining the effectiveness of management systems in healthcare institutions [6,10,12].

Analysis and Results.

The reviewed materials indicate that assessing the effectiveness of management systems in healthcare institutions is a complex, multifactorial process that requires a systematic approach. The effectiveness of personnel management systems is closely linked to institutional characteristics, human resource potential, service quality, and the level of resource utilization. The integration of these factors is considered a key prerequisite for making effective managerial decisions. It has been identified that making managerial decisions without sufficient justification or failing to implement them in a timely manner leads to a decrease in labor productivity, reduced employee engagement, and consequently has a negative impact on the economic performance of the institution.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The analysis confirms that evaluating the effectiveness of managerial decisions should encompass not only economic outcomes but also social aspects. This process should be carried out by jointly considering the degree of goal achievement, the optimal ratio between costs and results, as well as employee job satisfaction and social protection.

The Donabedian model, based on the interrelationship of structure, process, and outcome components, serves as a reliable scientific framework for assessing healthcare service quality and management effectiveness. Furthermore, a comprehensive analysis of socio-economic indicators—such as labor productivity, service volume, staff turnover, and employee satisfaction—plays a decisive role in optimizing management systems, improving service quality, and ensuring the sustainability of healthcare institutions.

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